

**EFFICACY AND ADEQUACY OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION
AND TRAINING (TVET) RESOURCES FOR REHABILITATION OF INMATES IN
CORRECTIONAL CENTRES IN NORTH-WEST NIGERIA.**

¹ Maryam Mannir Sani, ² P. S. Yaduma, ³A. M. Mshelia, ⁴J. M. Chedi

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Construction Technology Education,
Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Bauchi
State

D.O.I: 10.5281/zenodo.16360409

ARTICLE INFORMATION

ABSTRACT

Received: 18th April, 2025

Accepted: 22nd May, 2025

Published: 23rd June, 2025

KEYWORDS: Efficacy,
adequacy, technical, vocational
education

PUBLISHER: Empirical
Research Institute of Nigeria

This work is licensed under the Creative
Commons Attribution International
License (CC BY 4.0).

Open Access

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

this study assessed the efficacy and adequacy of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) resources for rehabilitation of inmates in correctional centres in north-west Nigeria. The study was guided by two specific objectives with their corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. In carrying out this investigation, evaluative survey research design was used. The population of the study was eleven thousand, six hundred and seventy-six (11,676) respondents comprised 83 Instructors, 9,600 Inmates and 1,993 Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. Based on the population, the sample size was three hundred and seventy-five (375) respondents, which comprised 83 instructors (the whole instructors were used because the number is manageable), 140 Inmates and 152 Ex-convicts were selected from the seven (7) correctional centres of the seven North-Western states using purposive sampling technique. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research question and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that: technical and vocational education training programmes modules are efficient, the instructors of the programmes are adequate and the facilities in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that: if adequate facilities were not provide in the correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the objectives of programme will not be accomplishes Therefore, the study recommended among others, that the Government and all relevant stakeholders should provide adequate facilities and encourage all instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria to ensure contents coverage as the training modules of the programme as scheduled.

1. Introduction

The hope of every Nation is to have a less crime environment, in every society there must be individuals who are not law abiding, they always try to break the law of the land, as a result of that every society established some rules in order to punish the culprit either by hanging, plugging, paying some fine, exile, confession, detained in one place for some period of time Garland, D. (2001). Correctional facilities across the globe were established for safekeeping of those incarcerated by a court awaiting judgment or serving a term for the purpose of rehabilitation to live a better and law-abiding life after incarceration. In our contemporary world, Correctional Institutions are established for the reduction of crimes, well-being and protection of societies and their properties (Nkwocha et al., 2020).

According to Obidiegwu et al (2021) defined a prison as a correctional institution where an offender, or those awaiting trials, are securely housed and given some sort of training while in confinement to prepare them for reintegration into larger society on release. A correctional centre can therefore be seen as a place where people are physically confined for committing a crime. The National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria (2018) expressed that correctional system is an integral part of the criminal justice system and serves as a custodial as well as a correctional institution. It also serves as a fundamental instrument for the protection, scrutiny, maintenance of the rule of law and social order.

The Nigerian correctional system derives its existence from several statutes among which are the ordinance of 1916; laws of Nigeria, 1948 and 1958 and the existing correctional centre decree no. 9 of 1972 Otu, S. E., & Anugwom, E. E. (2014). According to Opara (1998) the Nigerian correctional service is the promulgation of the correctional service decree no.9 of 1972. This was done in order to make the correctional service serve its triple purpose of confinement, reformation and rehabilitation. The decree according to the Annual correctional service report (1994) therefore specified the following objectives that should be performed in Nigerian correctional service.

- To keep safe custody of the inmates legally interned.
- To identify the causes of the anti-social behaviours, treat and reform inmates to become disciplined and law-abiding citizens of a free society.
- To train the inmates towards their rehabilitation on discharge and
- To generate funds to the government through correctional centre's farm and industry.

These objectives gave birth to the introduction of some directorates to carry out specialised functions needs to achieve the objectives of the correctional service. One such directorate is the directorate of inmates training and productivity. This is made agricultural and industry and charged with the responsibilities:

Technical and vocational training can be regarded as a systematic and scientific series of programs of acquiring knowledge and skills of a specific task in an industry. The main objective of technical and vocational programme is to train individuals on real-world skills and being able to perform tasks related to working in a particular industry (Akpoyibo & Ezechukwu, 2021). The

purpose of technical, vocational education and training is to equip people with the technical and professional skills needed for socio-economic and industrial development of the country. It is basically, a skill -based program designed for skill acquisition at a lower level of education (Greenspring-School, 2018).

Studies show that successful TVET interventions in prisons can increase inmates' employability, reduce their likelihood of reoffending, and promote self-reliance post-release (Ezeajughu, 2021).). However, without adequate tools, competent trainers, and appropriate curriculum, the potential of TVET in rehabilitation may be undermined. In the context of North-West Nigeria, characterized by high youth unemployment, security challenges, and weak correctional institutions, evaluating the effectiveness and sufficiency of TVET resources is imperative for both prison reform and societal development. To fill this literature gap, this study attempts to evaluate the technical and vocational education training programmes in correctional centres with specific reference to North-Western States of Nigeria Adebayo, A. M., & Oladeji, A. O. (2018). Recent studies that assessed the effectiveness of Technical and Vocational training in Correctional Centers in Nigeria using content, inputs process and products (CIPP) model for the study, it is considered a decision-making model that systematically collects information about strength and limitations in content or delivery to improve programme effectiveness or plan for future of the programme...

Statement of the Problem

The inmates are expected to leave the Correctional Centres well reformed and rehabilitated and with vocational skills that will enable them to adopt to the society and live a life of self-sustaining, self-sufficiency and self-reliance and also become productive members of the society.

Prior research investigations observed that technical and vocational training programs have significance influence on the successful rehabilitation and reformation and re-integration of ex-inmates into their respective immediate societies. Correctional service facilities across North-Western States of Nigeria are experiencing enormous administrative problems that hinder inmates' welfare packages, overcrowding of inmates beyond the capacity of the facilities, inadequate health care services, unhealthy kitchen environment and most importantly, the absence of Technical and Vocational Training equipment. This assertion was confirmed by the National Human Rights Commission in its 2018 Prison report documents, where it was narrated that Funtua Prisons, Katsina State did not have any form of Technical and Vocational Facilities in place. The other Correctional Centres visited in the North-West have a limited number of Technical and Vocational Facilities with a combination of the following Vocational facilities: carpentry unit, tailoring unit, iron work unit, saloon/barbing, laundry, shoe making and knitting.

Based on prior existing related literature reviewed in this study, it was observed that Technical and Vocational Training Programme encountered problems which served as impediments towards the proper achievement of the programs. Olajide (2023) identified that the problems affecting Technical and Vocational Training Programs in Nigeria include; inadequate funding, inadequate facilities, lack of teaching materials and learning aids, lack of private investors, negative perception of the society, slow pace of technological growth, and lack of adequate professionally trained educators to ensure proper curriculum development. However, there was no research carried out on the evaluation of technical and vocational education training program in correctional centres with special reference to north-western states in Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to evaluate the technical and vocational training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-west, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Ascertain the efficacy of the training modules of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the adequacy of instructors of Technical and Vocational Education.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent are the efficacy of the Training Modules Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are the adequacy of the instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-west Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested by the study.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts in regard to the efficacy of the training modules of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts in regard to adequacy of instructors and Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was used in the study. The study looked into the opinions and views of Instructors, Inmates and Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. To answer the research question, a structured questionnaire comprising 25 items was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the area. The reliability of the instrument was tested and it yielded a reliability index of 0.976. The population of the study was eleven thousand, six hundred and seventy-six (11,676) respondents comprised 83 Instructors, 9,600 Inmates and 1,993 Ex-convicts of the North-Western Correctional Centres. Based on the population, the sample size was three hundred and seventy-five (375) respondents, which comprised 83 instructors (the whole instructors were used because the number is manageable), 140 Inmates and 152 Ex-convicts were selected from the seven (7) correctional centres of the seven North-Western states using purposive sampling technique. 340 copies of the questionnaire were returned for data analysis. Therefore, the retrieval/response rate stands as 98% while the mortality rate stands as 2%. Hence, the analysis was computed based on 352 duly responded and retrieved. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents and answer the research questions and simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses stated in chapter one at 0.05 level of significance. Simple linear regression was used because the study is seeking impact of one

independent variable on one dependent variable.

Results

Results of Research Questions

The results of research questions were presented in Tables 1 to 4

Research Question 1

To what extent are the Technical and vocational Education Training programmes modules efficient in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria? This research question was answered using mean and standard deviation. **1.5** was used as a decision mean

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on the Extent to which the Technical and Vocational Education Training Programme Training Modules Efficient in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria

S/ N	Item Statement	X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X ₃	SD ₃	X _g	Rmk
1.	The instructions provided in TVET content for the use of basic tools are effective	3.1 0	.705	2.3 3	.714	2.4 5	.71 9	2.53	High Extent
2.	Training content prepares inmates for self-employment	3.1 3	.779	2.3 9	.745	2.2 9	.74 9	2.50	High Extent
3.	The practical training covers all necessary aspects of TVET	2.8 3	.722	2.3 1	.778	2.2 9	.74 9	2.41	Low Extent
4.	The theoretical training covers all important topics	2.9 1	.697	2.2 8	.759	2.2 0	.77 4	2.37	Low Extent
5.	Sufficient time is allocated for practical training.	3.0 6	.720	2.3 1	.729	2.2 6	.77 6	2.44	low Extent
6.	Instructors provide clear guidance on the use of equipment	2.9 7	.780	2.3 4	.745	2.3 1	.77 3	2.45	Low Extent
7.	Adequate time is allocated to cover the syllabus	2.8 6	.905	2.3 5	.788	2.4 8	.82 1	2.50	High Extent
8.	Instructors emphasize desired work habits	2.9 4	.883	2.4 1	.719	2.5 0	.69 1	2.55	High Extent

9.	The training program is of sufficient length	2.9 0	.837	2.4 0	.812	2.4 7	.76 7	2.53	High Extent
10.	Inmates demonstrate satisfactory performance in practical work	2.7 7	.837	2.3 4	.747	2.4 7	.65 9	2.48	Low Extent
11.	Instructors provide adequate supervision during project activities.	2.8 7	.797	2.5 1	.754	2.5 3	.68 0	2.59	High Extent
12.	The training content is relevant to the prison environment	2.9 0	.705	2.4 3	.760	2.4 8	.71 0	2.54	High Extent
13.	The training program is regularly reviewed to meet inmates' needs	2.7 6	.788	2.5 0	.800	2.4 8	.74 0	2.54	High Extent
14.	The language used in course materials is clear and understandable	2.7 7	.783	2.5 4	.781	2.6 0	.73 3	2.61	High Extent
15.	Inmates are adequately engaged with practical projects.	2.8 1	.889	2.5 4	.781	2.5 2	.73 0	2.59	High Extent
16.	The course content helps reform inmates' attitudes	2.9 0	.854	2.6 9	.738	2.7 2	.70 6	2.74	High Extent
17.	The course content prepares inmates for integration after discharge	2.8 0	.844	2.6 5	.767	2.6 7	.80 3	2.69	High Extent
18.	Inmates acquire trade skills within the specified period	2.7 9	.778	2.5 7	.779	2.5 2	.77 7	2.59	High Extent
19.	The course content helps inmates learn entrepreneurial skills	2.6 6	.946	2.4 8	.835	2.4 3	.81 0	2.50	High Extent
20.	The course content prepares inmates for self-employment	2.7 7	.951	2.2 9	.732	2.2 9	.69 0	2.39	Low Extent
21.	The course content motivates inmates to acquire necessary skills	2.8 6	.856	2.5 4	.693	2.4 9	.74 0	2.58	High Extent
22.	The course content prepares	2.9	.737	2.5	1.03	2.4	.69	2.61	High

	inmates for examinations	1		9	8	8	1		Extent
23.	Inmates are provided with industrial attachment opportunities	3.1	.773	2.5	.834	2.5	.82	2.66	High Extent
		6		5		3	1		
24.	The community appreciates inmates' practical work	2.8	.785	2.4	.759	2.3	.74	2.50	High Extent
		6		2		9	1		
25.	The course content accommodates individual differences among inmates	2.5	.911	2.5	.816	2.4	.77	2.53	High Extent
		6		5		9	7		
	Cluster Mean	2.8	.810	2.45	.776	2.45	.745	2.54	High Extent
		7							

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on to what extent are the Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes modules efficient in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria. The table showed the mean of Instructors ranging from 2.66 to 3.16, the standard deviation also ranges from .697 to .951, the mean of Inmates also ranges from 2.28 to 2.69, the standard deviation ranges from .693 to 1.038 and the mean of Ex-convicts ranges from 2.20 to 2.67, the standard deviation also ranges from .659 to .821 respectively. The cluster mean of Instructors is 2.87, Inmates is 2.45 while that of Ex-convicts is 2.45, the grand mean of the respondents is 2.54 which means Technical and Vocational Training programmes contents are efficient in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Research question 2

To what extent are the instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres adequate in North-West, Nigeria. *1.5 was used as a decision mean*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on to what Extent are the Instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training Programmes in Correctional Centre North-West, Nigeria Adequate

S/N	Item Statement	X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X ₃	SD ₃	X _g	Remark
1.	The Carpentry training program provides inmates with sufficient practical skills.	3.09	.697	2.51	.735	2.50	.730	2.62	Adequate
2.	The Tailoring training program is relevant to the needs of the local community.	3.11	.772	2.62	.734	2.52	.777	2.68	Adequate
3.	The Ironwork training program equips inmates with necessary safety skills.	3.00	.742	2.48	.826	2.50	.740	2.59	Adequate

4.	The Cap making training program provides inmates with entrepreneurial skills.	2.87	.815	2.53	.800	2.49	.711	2.58	Adequate
5.	The Cap washing training program is effective in teaching inmate's laundry skills.	2.89	.877	2.62	.809	2.57	.765	2.65	Adequate
6.	The Laundry services training program provides inmates with job-ready skills.	2.77	.783	2.33	.704	2.44	.718	2.46	Less Adequate
7.	The Women's salon training program is relevant to the needs of female inmates.	2.90	.801	2.29	.842	2.25	.773	2.39	Less Adequate
8.	The Barbing salon training program provides inmates with necessary grooming skills.	2.69	.910	2.33	.852	2.33	.785	2.40	Less Adequate
9.	The Poultry training program teaches inmates sustainable poultry management practices.	2.73	.867	2.26	.792	2.31	.782	2.37	Less Adequate
10.	The Farming training program teaches inmates sustainable agricultural practices.	3.10	.837	2.50	1.083	2.31	.800	2.54	Adequate
11.	The Car wash training program provides inmates with hands-on experience.	3.09	.775	2.34	.685	2.43	.783	2.53	Adequate
12.	The Electrical installation training program equips inmates with necessary technical skills	3.00	.816	2.35	.873	2.35	.744	2.48	Less Adequate
	Cluster Mean	2.94	.808	2.43	.811	2.42	.759	2.52	Adequate

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on to what extent are the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria. The table showed the mean of Instructors ranging from 2.69 to 3.11, the standard deviation also ranges from .697 to .910, the mean of Inmates also ranges from 2.26 to 2.62, the standard deviation ranges from .734 to 1.038 and the mean of Ex-convicts ranges from 2.25 to 2.57, the standard deviation also ranges from .711 to .800 respectively. The cluster mean of Instructors is 2.94, Inmates is 2.43 while that of Ex-convicts is 2.42, the grand mean of the respondents is 2.52 which means the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria are adequate.

Research Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference among the mean responses of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the efficiency training modules in Technical and vocational Education Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria. ANOVA analysis was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on there is no Significant Difference Among the Mean Response of the Instructors, Inmates and ex-convicts on the training modules' Efficiency in Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	9.929	2	4.965	57.164	.000	Rejected
Within Groups	30.326	350	.087			
Total	40.326	352				

ANOVA analysis result in Table 3 revealed that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the content efficiency in Technical and vocational Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria with the F-value of 57.164 and the p- value of .000. Since the p- value is less than the confidence level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 (95%) confidence level. This implies that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the content efficiency in Technical and vocational Training programmes in correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the adequacy of instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria. ANOVA analysis was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance

Table 4: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on there is No Significant Difference among the Mean Response of the Instructors, Inmates and Ex-Convicts on the Adequacy of Instructors of Technical and Vocational Training Programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	14.736	2	7.368	59.358	.000	Rejected
Within Groups	43.446	350	.124			
Total	58.182	352				

ANOVA analysis results in Table 10 revealed that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the adequacy of instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria with the F-value of 59.358 and the p- value of .000. Since the p- value is less than the confidence level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 (95%) confidence level. This implies that there is significant difference among the mean response of the instructors, inmates and ex-convicts on the adequacy of instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

The study is an investigation on the efficacy and adequacy of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) resources for rehabilitation of inmates in correctional centres in north-west Nigeria, based on two key areas which include; training modules and adequacy of instructors of Technical and Vocational Education Training programmes in correctional Centres. Therefore, two (2) research objectives, two (2) research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and guided the conduct of the study.

In general, the study revealed that that Technical and Vocational Training programmes training modules are efficient in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria are adequate, the Technical and Vocational Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate, the instructional methods of training (process) of technical and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are effective and The TVET training programmes in rehabilitating inmates in correctional centers in North-west, Nigeria is effective..

Conclusions

From the available data, the study revealed that Technical and Vocational Training programmes training modules are efficient in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria, the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria are adequate, the Technical and Vocational Training programmes facilities in Correctional Centres in North-West, Nigeria are less adequate, the instructional methods of training (process) of technical

and vocational training programmes in the correctional centres in North-West, Nigeria are effective and The TVET training programmes in rehabilitating inmates in correctional centers in North- west, Nigeria is effective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The Government and all relevant stakeholders should encourage all instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria to ensure contents coverage as the contents of the programme is efficient.
- ii. The Government and all relevant stake holders should be organising refresher training for all the instructors of Technical and Vocational Training programmes in Correctional Centre in North-West, Nigeria.

REFERENCE

- Akpoiyibo, F.E., & Ezechukwu, O.A. (2021). *Rethinking Vocational Education in Nigeria*. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 4(9), 64-70.
- Ezeajughu, M.C. (2021). *Evaluating Rehabilitation Programmes and Crime Relapse Among Inmates in Two Selected Maximum-Security Prisons in Nigeria*. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies*, 4(1), 147 – 154.
- Greenspring School, (2018). *The need for Vocational Education in Nigeria*. Retrieved from <http://enrol.greenspringsschool.com/the-need-for-vocational-in-Nigeria>
- National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria (2018). *Prison Report Document: 2018*.
- Nkwocha, D.I., Omoyibo, K., Yesufu, A.R., & Adegoke, A.T. (2020). *Prisons and Correctional Institutions in Nigeria*. National Open University of Nigeria.
- Obidiegwu, U.J, Ogbunugwor, A.U. & Madu, C.O. (2021). *Perceptions of Inmates on the Implementation of Rehabilitative Programmes on Basic Literacy Education in the Custodies in Imo State*. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 7, 400-411.
- Olajide, F. (2023). *10 Problems of Vocational Education in Nigeria and Possible Solutions*. Retrieved June 6, 2023, from <https://infoguidenigeria.com/vocational-education-nigeria/>
- Opara, A.T. (1998). *Criminology and Penology*. Cel-Bez & Co. Publisher.
- Garland, D. (2001). *The Culture of Control: Crime and Social Order in Contemporary Society*. University of Chicago Press.

- Adebayo, A. M., & Oladeji, A. O. (2018). Vocational and technical education in Nigerian prisons: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(14), 111–116.
- Otu, S. E., & Anugwom, E. E. (2014). The Prison System and the Problem of Recidivism in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Management Review*, 9(1), 200–214.